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UDK: 342.726-053.2(497.11)

UDK: 341.231.14-053.2(497.11)

UDK: 342.565.2(497.11)

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17811868

USTAVNOPRAVNA ZAŠTITA PRAVA DETETA: STANDARDI, OBAVEZE I REALNOST PRIMENE KONVENCIJE O PRAVIMA DETETA

Autorke u radu analiziraju delotvornost ustavnopravnih i institucionalnih mehanizama zaštite prava deteta u Republici Srbiji kroz primenu standarda „najboljeg interesa deteta“, koji predstavlja osnovni međunarodni i ustavni kriterijum u svim postupcima koji se tiču dece. Centralno istraživačko pitanje jeste da li savremeni normativni okvir i institucionalna praksa obezbeđuju stvarnu, a ne samo deklarativnu zaštitu prava deteta, u kontekstu primene Konvencije UN o pravima deteta. Posebna pažnja posvećena je ulozi Ustavnog suda Republike Srbije u zaštiti prava deteta, kako kroz kontrolu ustavnosti zakona, tako i kroz odlučivanje po ustavnim žalbama u predmetima koji se neposredno odnose na dete. Analizira se da li Sud dosledno primenjuje standard najboljeg interesa deteta kao ustavnopravni korektiv, te u kojoj meri njegova praksa doprinosi ujednačavanju standarda zaštite u sudskim i upravnim postupcima. Iako je domaći pravni sistem u značajnoj meri usaglašen sa međunarodnim standardima i iako se poslednjih godina beleže pozitivni pomaci — uključujući profesionalizaciju organa starateljstva, unapređenje sudske prakse, jačanje preventivnih mehanizama, razvoj specijalizovanih postupaka i aktivniju ulogu nezavisnih institucija — i dalje postoji izražen jaz između normi i realnosti. Kao ključni izazovi identifikuju se: neujednačena primena standarda najboljeg interesa deteta, nepostojanje jasnih i ujednačenih kriterijuma u procenama, nedovoljna koordinacija među institucijama, predugo trajanje postupaka i povremeno neadekvatna primena međunarodnih standarda u sudskim odlukama. Zaključak naglašava potrebu za daljim jačanjem institucionalnih kapaciteta, ujednačavanjem sudske prakse, aktivnijom ulogom Ustavnog suda i snažnijim preventivnim mehanizmima, kako bi se standard najboljeg interesa deteta dosledno i delotvorno primenio u svim postupcima koji utiču na dete.

Ključne reči: najbolji interes deteta, Ustavni sud, prava deteta, sudska zaštita, institucionalni okvir.

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CONSTITUTIONAL PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD: STANDARDS, OBLIGATIONS, AND THE REALITY OF IMPLEMENTING THE CONVENTION ON THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD

This paper analyzes the effectiveness of constitutional and institutional mechanisms for the protection of the rights of the child in the Republic of Serbia through the application of the "best interests of the child" standard, as a fundamental international and constitutional criterion in all proceedings concerning children. The central research question is whether the contemporary normative framework and institutional practice ensure genuine, rather than merely declaratory, protection of children's rights within the context of implementing the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. Special attention is given to the role of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Serbia in the protection of children's rights, both through constitutional review of legislation and through adjudication on constitutional complaints in cases directly concerning children. The paper examines whether the Court consistently applies the best interests of the child as a constitutional corrective, and to what extent its jurisprudence contributes to the harmonization of child protection standards in judicial and administrative proceedings. Although the domestic legal system is largely aligned with international standards and although there have been positive developments in recent years, particularly in terms of the professionalization of guardianship authorities, the improvement of judicial practice, the strengthening of preventive mechanisms, the development of specialized procedures, and the increasingly active role of independent institutions, a significant gap between norms and reality persists. The key challenges identified include: inconsistent application of the best interests of the child standard, the absence of clear and uniform criteria in assessments, insufficient coordination among institutions, excessively long proceedings, and at times inadequate application of international standards in judicial decisions. The conclusion emphasizes the need for further strengthening of institutional capacities, harmonization of case law, a more active role of the Constitutional Court, and stronger preventive mechanisms, in order to consistently and effectively apply the best interests of the child standard in all proceedings affecting the child.

Keywords: best interests of the child, Constitutional Court, children's rights, judicial protection, institutional framework.